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Abnormalities of Broiler Chickens Reared Under the Deep Litter System: Health, Welfare and Management Implications

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Introduction

The deep litter system is commonly used in broiler production because it is inexpensive, allows for unrestricted mobility and creates a cozy environment for quick growth. Poor management, on the other hand, can result in anomalies, health issues and lower farm profits. Identifying these issues early and modifying management approaches leads to improved outcomes.

1. Bones and Skeletal Deformities

Broilers grow quickly, thus robust bone growth is necessary. Leg difficulties in the deep litter system might occur as a result of hard flooring, nutritional imbalance or damp litter.

Common problems:

- **Rickets:** It is a metabolic disease that causes due to deficiency of calcium, phosphorus and vitamin D imbalances. It leads to soft, weak and bent bones in broilers.
- **Tibial dyschondroplasia:** Tibial dyschondroplasia is a cartilage development abnormality in the tibia that causes swelling, lameness and difficulty standing or walking.
- **Splayed legs:** It is a kind of abnormalities in broiler in which legs of chicks extends widely owing to frailty. This condition makes the difficult to gain the body weight.

Preventive measures:

- **Provide balanced mineral and vitamin supplements:** Most of the metabolic disease can be prevented by supplying optimal amount of nutrients like calcium, phosphorus and essential vitamins.
- **Avoid overcrowding and uneven flooring:** The overcrowding of the farm should be avoided, it causes a kind of feeding competition that causes trampling and stress in flock.

2. Respiratory Distress

Dust and moisture content in the litter mainly cause to raise of ammonia levels, which leads to the respiratory distress. Having respiratory distress causes breathing difficulties, especially when ventilation is poor.

Frequently observed issues:

- **Infectious bronchitis:** It is a contagious respiratory illness that causes coughing, sneezing and decreased development, particularly in crowded or poorly ventilated environments.
- **Chronic respiratory disease:** Most of the respiratory disease is caused by Mycoplasma. That shows the symptoms of coughing, nasal discharge, and poor feed conversion.

Control Measures:

- **Maintain good ventilation:** Improves air quality by removing dust, moisture and harmful gases, helping birds breathe comfortably and grow better.
- **Keep ammonia levels low:** Ammonia level in the shed of broiler farm causes a major impact and its level should be maintained at minimal point.

3. Digestive Disorders

Some birds may ingest bedding material or suffer digestive troubles due to feed contamination, stress, or infection.

Common digestive issues:

- **Coccidiosis:** It is a parasitic illness that causes bloody diarrhea, poor

development and increased mortality under damp litter conditions.

- **Necrotic enteritis:** It is a bacterial infection of the intestine that causes tissue destruction, abrupt death and decreased feed efficiency. It is commonly accompanied with coccidiosis.
- **Diarrhea:** It refers to loose or watery droppings induced by illness, feed imbalance or stress. This can quickly make litter moist and raise disease risk.
- **Crop or gizzard impaction:** It occurs when feed or bedding material blocks the crop or gizzard, leading to lower intake, poor development and digestive pain.

Management Suggestions:

- These can be prevented by maintain feed hygiene on regular basis.
- By using of anticoccidials or coccidiosis vaccines, most of the abnormalities can be prevented.
- Keep feeders and drinkers clean and accessible. The litter moisture should be maintained at 20–30%.

4. Skin and Foot Abnormalities

Skin and foot lesions are often linked to wet or dirty litter, affecting both welfare and carcass quality.

Common conditions:

- **Footpad dermatitis:** It is caused by damp or muddy litter, leading to lesions or ulcers on the underside of the feet. This reduces comfort and carcass quality.
- **Hock burns:** It occur when fast-growing broilers are exposed to ammonia and moisture, resulting in darkened inflammatory areas around the joints.
- **Breast blisters:** These are fluid-filled swellings on the breast produced by prolonged contact with moist bedding or hard surfaces. This can compromise meat quality and appearance

Prevention:

- By using of absorbent litter materials, moisture can be reduced that prevents fungal growth.
- Adjust drinkers to prevent water wastage.
- Always monitor flock weight and stock density as per standard area for proper housing managements.

5. Infectious Diseases Associated with Deep Litter

If litter is not replaced or composted between batches, harmful organisms can multiply.

Major diseases include:

- **Coccidiosis:** It is a kind parasitic infestation that mainly affects the intestines and causes diarrhea, poor development and shows high mortality.
- **Salmonellosis:** It is a bacterial infestation that mainly affects the digestive tract along with septicemia. It caused diarrhea and ultimate poor performance of the flock.
- **Colibacillosis:** It is an illness produced by E. coli bacteria that can lead to respiratory difficulties, septicemia or peritonitis. It is often linked to stress and poor hygiene.
- **Mycoplasma infections:** It can cause coughing, nasal discharge and impaired feed efficiency, particularly in poorly ventilated or overcrowded environments.
- **Fowl pox:** It is a viral illness that causes nodular skin lesions or diphtheritic plaques in the mouth and upper airway. It is spread by mosquitoes and direct contact.

Control through:

- **Biosecurity:** It controls the regulating of people and wild birds to enters into the shed that may transmit disease to flocks.
- **Proper sanitation:** Regular cleaning and disinfection reduces pathogens in the environment, that nullify the risk of infections.

- **Vaccination programs:** Vaccination programs protect birds from common illnesses and boost immunity and enhancing proper body weight.

6. Future Perspectives

- A large number of advancement has been done in poultry framing such as litter moisture sensors, ammonia monitoring systems, and AI-based gait analysis that can be used to identify any abnormalities in the shed.
- All these advanced techniques can enhance the productivity of deep litter systems.

Conclusion

The deep litter system of poultry farming is an integral component of part of broiler production that mainly depends on its proper management and administration. Skeletal anomalies, respiratory difficulties, digestive issues, skin lesions and infectious infections can be greatly reduced by implementing integrated dietary, environmental and biosecurity initiatives. By applying advanced technologies and AI based sensors in the farm can promote better broiler production that ultimately increase the production and economic sustainability.